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AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

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Disclaimer

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¹ Due to the nature of this deliverable, all PLIADES partners have provided feedback and revisions.

Executive Summary

This document reports the dissemination and communication activities undertaken up to December 2024 (M12) as part of the PLIADES project. These activities align with Task 8.1 “Dissemination Plan and Marketing & Promotional Material” and Task 8.2 “Dissemination and Communication Activities including portal & social media presence” under Work Package 8: “Dissemination & Exploitation, Standardization and Liaison”.

The report details the creation and implementation of visual identity elements, the use of various dissemination channels (e.g., web portal, social networks, newsletters, and publications), and the synergies established with other projects. Progress against predefined performance indicators is also outlined, offering insights into the reach and impact of these activities.

The last part of the report outlines the activities that will lead to the development of the PLIADES training program, reporting activities of T8.5. The training program will be focused on educating the current (and future) end users of the PLIADES ecosystem on data security issues. The material for the training content will be closely related to the PLIADES developments that negotiate data security topics or are focused on data security implementations, so that it can act as a means of disseminating the project’s solutions at the same time. Potential questions/doubts/concerns of the future end-users will be addressed with the developed training content.

In this section of the document, the initial plan that has been designed for the creation of the training content is presented, outlining the next actions and foreseen timeline for the completion of each step. Surveys and desk research results will be used to decide on specific learning objectives for the target audiences. Iterations and improvements are foreseen, as the training content and selected training method will be validated within the consortium partners at first, before sharing it with external end-users.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
Table of Contents.....	4
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	6
List of Terms and Definitions	7
1 Introduction	8
1.1 Scope of the deliverable	8
1.2 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables	8
1.3 Document Structure.....	8
2 Dissemination activities	10
2.1 Project Identity and Branding	10
2.1.1 Logo.....	10
2.1.2 Templates.....	11
2.2 Marketing Pack and Promotional Press Kit.....	11
2.2.1 Leaflet.....	12
2.2.2 Poster	13
2.2.3 Slide-based Presentation	14
2.3 Dissemination channels	15
2.3.1 PLIADES website.....	15
2.3.2 Social media accounts - Twitter Page, LinkedIn Page, YouTube Channel.....	19
2.3.3 Press releases.....	23
2.3.4 Newsletters	24
2.3.5 Short videos	34
2.3.6 Workshops/ Conferences/ Demonstrations	35
2.3.7 Publications.....	36
2.3.8 Zenodo community	36
2.4 Synergies	38
3 Performance indicators and monitoring.....	39
4 Training programs initial plan and guidelines.....	41
4.1 Background and training needs	41
4.2 Available training methods	42
4.3 Training Program Development Methodology	43
4.3.1 Stage 1: Desk research, specification of the training context.....	44
4.3.2 Stage 2: Survey targeting the internal stakeholders.....	44

4.3.3	1 st version of the training program	45
4.3.4	Validation within the consortium	46
4.3.5	Iterations and final release	46
5	Conclusions	47
6	Appendix	48
6.1	Deliverable template	48
6.2	Presentation template	50
6.3	Newsletter template	52
6.4	List of dissemination activities	54

List of Figures

Figure 1. PLIADES project logo	10
Figure 2. PLIADES logo colour pallet	10
Figure 3. PLIADES logo in different backgrounds.....	11
Figure 4. Slide A of the PLIADES leaflet.....	12
Figure 5. Slide B of the PLIADES leaflet.....	13
Figure 6. PLIADES poster.....	14
Figure 7. Website analytics	16
Figure 8. Screenshot of the Cookies Manager pop-up, illustrating the options for managing user preferences.	18
Figure 9. LinkedIn analytics showing follower growth.....	20
Figure 10. LinkedIn analytics showing post interactions	20
Figure 11. Views on the PLIADES posts of X.....	21
Figure 12. Screenshot of the YouTube channel homepage, showcasing available videos.....	22
Figure 13. First page of the PLIADES launch press release	23
Figure 14. Second page of the PLIADES launch press release, showcasing consortium members and project objectives.....	24
Figure 15. PLIADES newsletters uploaded on the project web portal upon release	25
Figure 16. Screenshot of the subscription form available on the PLIADES website	32
Figure 17. Newsletter #1 distribution and engagement statistics (open rates, clicks) from Mailchimp	32
Figure 18. Newsletter #2 distribution and engagement statistics (open rates, clicks) from Mailchimp	33
Figure 19. PLIADES Zenodo community.....	37
Figure 20: Training Program Development Proposed Methodology and timeline	44

List of Tables

Table 1. Definitions	7
Table 2. Preview of the survey on the training content that will be shared with the partners	45

List of Terms and Definitions

Table 1. Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

Deliverable D8.2, titled “Dissemination and Communication Activities Report (v1)”, provides an overview of the dissemination and communication activities carried out within the PLIADES project during its first year. These activities have been guided by the Dissemination and Communication Plan outlined in Deliverable D8.1. The overarching goals include:

- Raising awareness about the project’s objectives, methodologies, and results among diverse stakeholders, including policymakers, industry leaders, academic researchers, and the general public.
- Establishing robust communication channels to keep stakeholders informed and engaged.
- Maximising the project’s visibility and accessibility to its target audience.
- Encouraging the adoption and practical application of PLIADES innovations.
- Creating strategies to ensure long-term impact and scalability of the project's outcomes beyond its duration.

1.2 Relation to other Activities and Deliverables

The dissemination and communication activities in D8.2 are aligned with other key deliverables and activities within the PLIADES project to ensure consistency and effectiveness. Below are the key connections:

- D8.1 (Dissemination and Communication Plan): The activities in D8.2 follow the strategy, objectives, and KPIs set in D8.1, ensuring that dissemination efforts remain focused and aligned with the project's goals.
- Exploitation Strategy (D8.3, D8.4): Dissemination in D8.2 helps pave the way for future exploitation by raising awareness of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). These efforts will support the exploitation pathways to be defined in D8.3 and D8.4, thereby increasing visibility and interest in project outcomes.
- Online Presence (website, social media, newsletters): The project’s website, social media, and newsletters are key tools for promoting events, publications, and KERs. D8.2 tracks the effectiveness of these channels, ensuring continuous improvement.
- Contributions from Other Work Packages (WPs): As the project progresses and more results become available, dissemination activities will draw on content from WPs 3, 4, 6, and 7. This will include technical outputs from pilots, privacy-preserving methods, and Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- Training and Capacity Building (D8.5, D8.6): Early awareness-raising activities from D8.2 support engagement for the later training deliverables (D8.5, D8.6) by building an audience and informing stakeholders about PLIADES results.

This interconnected approach strengthens the project’s outreach, ensuring all dissemination activities contribute to broader project objectives and support future exploitation.

1.3 Document Structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1. Introduction: Details the scope and structure of the report.

- Chapter 2. Dissemination activities: Discusses the branding, dissemination channels, collaborations, and efforts across various platforms.
- Chapter 3. Performance indicators and monitoring: Presents the key performance indicators (KPIs) for dissemination and communication, along with progress towards achieving these targets.
- Chapter 4. Training programs initial plan and guidelines: Outlines the plan for the development of training programs related to the dissemination of knowledge and results generated by the PLIADES project.
- Chapter 5. Conclusions: Summarises the outcomes and suggests areas for improvement.
- Chapter 6. Appendix: Includes supporting materials, such as templates for deliverables, presentations, newsletters, and a list of dissemination activities.

2 Dissemination activities

2.1 Project Identity and Branding

A distinct graphical identity has been designed for PLIADES to ensure consistent and professional branding across all dissemination materials. This includes the creation of a project logo, a colour palette, and templates for presentations, deliverables, and promotional materials. These elements serve to enhance recognition of the PLIADES project among stakeholders and ensure a unified presentation of the project's activities.

2.1.1 Logo

A visually appealing logo was designed to serve as the cornerstone of the PLIADES project's branding. It has been prominently featured across all project-related platforms and documents, including the website, social media, deliverables, presentations etc. The logo's consistent use enhances the visibility of PLIADES activities, creating a cohesive and recognisable visual identity.

Figure 1. PLIADES project logo

Primary Colours: The logo incorporates a specific palette that reflects the project's values and objectives.

Figure 2. PLIADES logo colour pallet

Variations: Multiple logo variations were developed to ensure adaptability across different backgrounds and formats.

Figure 3. PLIADES logo in different backgrounds

2.1.2 Templates

To maintain uniformity in all communications, standardised templates were developed for project documentation, presentations, and newsletters. These templates, aligned with PLIADES branding, were distributed to all consortium partners to ensure consistency throughout the project lifecycle.

Especially, these templates include:

- Document template (see Section 6.1): A template for deliverables and reports, featuring the PLIADES logo and colour scheme to ensure a professional and consistent layout.
- PowerPoint presentation template (see Section 6.2): Designed for workshops, conferences, and internal meetings, the slide deck reflects the project's branding while accommodating diverse content needs.
- Newsletter template (see Section 6.3): A user-friendly and mobile-responsive format designed for periodic updates, ensuring compatibility with various devices for maximum accessibility.

By utilising these templates, the PLIADES consortium ensures that all project outputs are cohesive, professional, and aligned with the project's visual identity.

2.2 Marketing Pack and Promotional Press Kit

To effectively communicate the PLIADES project's objectives and progress, a comprehensive marketing pack and promotional press kit have been developed. These materials ensure consistent messaging and provide visually engaging resources for dissemination.

2.2.1 Leaflet

A project leaflet was created for distribution at conferences, workshops, and within partner organisations. This leaflet provides a clear and concise overview of PLIADES, helping to engage a broader audience. It provides a concise overview of the PLIADES project, including:

- The project’s aims and objectives.
- A summary of its case studies.
- Information about the consortium partners.
- Key project data, including EU funding acknowledgements, contact details, and links to the official website and social media.

Future iterations of the leaflet will focus on presenting the project’s outcomes and results, with updated versions planned for the final six months of the project.

The following figures show an image of both sides of the leaflet.

Target Values

Scientific: Research and development of innovative tools and standards

- that address critical challenges in data creation, storage, ownership, discovery, and disposal across diverse data spaces.

Societal: Produce greener data and enhanced services and products

- using advanced yet eco-friendly data processing methods for data generation,
- and improve everyday life through personalised healthcare products, smart vehicles, etc.

Economic/ Technological: The deployment of the PLIADES framework aims to:

- reduce resource requirements for data acquisition,
- improve technological solutions and promote advancements across multiple industries, through the utilisation of vast amounts of high-quality data,
- enable synergies between multiple data spaces for development of innovative technologies.

Who are we?

27 Partners across 10 EU Member States & Switzerland
 Consortium Breakdown: 12 RTOs, 10 SMEs, 5 NPOs

Project timeline

Start Date: January 1st, 2024
End Date: June 30th, 2027 (42 months)

Important Milestones:

- Definition of system architecture (2024)
- Preliminary deployment of framework (2026)
- Launch of PLIADES data spaces (2026)
- Pilot testing and evaluation (2027)

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles
 Optimization and Data Spaces
 Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

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Figure 4. Slide A of the PLIADES leaflet

Mission

PLIADES stands for an advanced AI-enabled framework for Full Data Lifecycles Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration. Our mission is to revolutionize how data is utilised across various sectors, from mobility to healthcare, manufacturing to energy, and beyond.

PLIADES envisions a future where diverse sectors are seamlessly interconnected, enhancing efficiency and interoperability.

We aim to provide cutting-edge data and services that drive advancements in Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Advanced Driver Assistance & Autonomous Driving (ADAS/AD), and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI).

Objectives

The specific objectives of PLIADES are to:

- Research and develop novel models, abstractions, and methods for environmentally friendly, context- and human-factors-aware creation of vast amounts of data for mobility, green deal, energy, industrial and healthcare dataspaces.
- Advance data privacy, security, trustworthiness and sovereignty, enabling data owners to safely determine how their information is collected, stored and used.
- Promote advanced data decentralisation and further advance AI-boosted brokers.
- Generate advanced Data Spaces connectors to extend the scope of data spaces interoperability, encompassing full data life cycles into existing data reference architectures.
- Facilitate novel data processing and analytics services to ensure data privacy, trustworthiness, security, resilience, re-use and disposal.
- Deploy the proposed framework in diverse use cases, focusing on transportation, energy, manufacturing, healthcare and green deal sectors.
- Develop new business models that promote data sharing and re-use and establish synergies with other EU initiatives.

Use cases

PLIADES outcomes will utilise different types of data spanning six use cases, focusing on diverse dataspace, such as :

- data from smart vehicles to improve their ADAS/ AD & CCAM functions and energy management (mobility dataspace),
- patient/doctor HRI data to improve service robots' HRI effectiveness and patient data to improve diagnostic & prognostic clinical models for personalised medicine services (healthcare dataspace),
- manufacturing data to improve zero-waste manufacturing, predictive maintenance and HRI (industrial dataspace).

Figure 5. Slide B of the PLIADES leaflet

Available online: <https://www.pliades-project.eu/pliades-brochure/>

2.2.2 Poster

An A3 poster was developed (Figure 6) to visually summarise the PLIADES project. It highlights key messages, objectives, and consortium partners, serving as a focal point at events, workshops, and conferences. The poster is accessible online and will be updated periodically to incorporate the latest project developments.

Figure 6. PLIADES poster

Available online: <https://www.pliades-project.eu/pliades-poster/>

2.2.3 Slide-based Presentation

To address the needs of diverse audiences, two types of slide-based presentations have been prepared:

- Short Standard Presentation: This Designed for a general audience, this concise deck introduces the project's objectives and activities (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/pliades-presentation-project-overview/>)
- Extended Presentation: A detailed version for technical experts, policymakers, and other specialised stakeholders. It provides in-depth insights into the project's methodologies and progress.

Both presentations are available in English and are regularly updated to reflect the project's latest achievements. They are distributed to all consortium partners for use at relevant events and engagements.

2.3 Dissemination channels

2.3.1 PLIADES website

The PLIADES project website (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/>) serves as the central hub for all information related to the project, ensuring a cohesive and accessible platform for dissemination and communication. The website is designed to cater to a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, industry professionals, academic researchers, and the general public. It aims to provide comprehensive and up-to-date information on the project's objectives, progress, results, and impact. The website is regularly updated with news, events, publications, public deliverables and multimedia resources, with direct integration to the project's social media channels (X and YouTube). Additionally, a "News" section has been implemented to share articles related to PLIADES and its broader objectives, written by project partners and contributors.

Website Development and Maintenance

During the first 12 months of the project, the following tasks were completed to establish and maintain the website:

- Booking the domain names and setting up IT infrastructure.
- Defining content and website structure.
- Publishing and regularly updating news, events, and project results.

Performance and Analytics

The website's performance has been monitored using analytics tools to assess its reach and user engagement.

Figure 7. Website analytics

Some insights:

- Between February 2024 and December 2024, the website recorded 1.350 sessions from 781 unique users.
- Key user acquisition channels include:
 - Direct traffic: 560 sessions.
 - Organic search: 124 sessions.
 - Social media referrals: 60 sessions.
 - Other referrals: 37 sessions.
- The most popular countries among our audience are Greece (242 users), Spain (191 users), Germany (47 users), Czechia (42 users), United States (39), Italy (28 users), Austria (26 users), Ireland (26 users) and Netherlands (18).
- The information on the most visited pages demonstrates that apart from the landing page which contains information about the project concept and objectives, visitors are mostly in the PLIADES “News” page, “Media” pages, where the dissemination material contained, and “Partners” page.

The following figures provide a visual representation of website statistics:

- Geographic distribution of users, highlighting the most active countries (e.g., Greece, Spain, Germany).

- Breakdown of the most visited pages, with high traffic observed on the landing page, News section, and Media page.

Cookies Manager

To ensure compliance with GDPR and the ePrivacy Directive, the PLIADES website incorporates a comprehensive Cookies Manager. This feature is designed to meet all legal requirements for managing cookies while prioritising transparency and user control.

According to GDPR and ePrivacy Directive regulations, websites must:

- Obtain users’ explicit consent before using any cookies, except those strictly necessary for the website’s operation.

- Provide clear and specific information about each cookie’s purpose and the data it tracks, presented in simple and accessible language.
- Record and securely store user consent for audit and compliance purposes.
- Ensure that users can access the website’s services even if they decline optional cookies.
- Offer users the ability to easily withdraw or modify their consent at any time.

In alignment with these requirements, the PLIADES website has established a detailed Privacy and Cookies Policy (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/privacy-cookie-policy/>). This policy explains the types of data collected via cookies and their intended use. The Cookies Manager:

1. **Consent Management:** Enables users to approve or reject cookies through an intuitive interface before any non-essential cookies are activated.
2. **Transparency:** Clearly communicates the purpose of each cookie, ensuring users are fully informed before giving consent.
3. **Access Guarantee:** Grants users access to all website features, regardless of their cookie preferences.
4. **User Control:** Provides a persistent cookies icon, always visible in the bottom-left corner of the screen, allowing users to revisit and update their choices effortlessly.

The following figure provides a visual representation of the Cookies Manager:

Figure 8. Screenshot of the Cookies Manager pop-up, illustrating the options for managing user preferences.

This robust Cookies Manager ensures the PLIADES website adheres to GDPR standards while fostering user trust through transparency and convenience.

Next Steps

To further enhance website traffic and engagement, the following actions are planned:

- **Content Improvement:** Publishing detailed use-case results and creating a promotional video to attract more organic traffic.

- **Search Engine Optimisation (SEO):** Improving metadata and keywords to increase visibility in search engines.
- **Backlink Generation:** Building partnerships to secure external links that drive referral traffic.

2.3.2 Social media accounts - Twitter Page, LinkedIn Page, YouTube Channel

The PLIADES project has established an active presence on social media platforms, including **X (formerly Twitter)**, **LinkedIn**, and **YouTube**, to effectively disseminate updates, engage with stakeholders, and foster a broader community around the project. These platforms provide essential tools for reaching diverse audiences, from industry professionals and policymakers to academic researchers and the general public.

Social Media Strategy

The social media strategy focuses on:

- Sharing project updates, milestones, and results in an engaging and accessible manner.
- Promoting partner activities and events to showcase collaboration within the consortium.
- Engaging with relevant stakeholders to encourage discussions and strengthen the project's network.
- Disseminating newsletters, press releases, and multimedia content to maximise outreach.

Platform Overviews

1. **LinkedIn** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/pliades-project>):
 - Targets professionals, researchers, and industry stakeholders.
 - Focuses on in-depth updates, project highlights, and networking opportunities.
 - Has steadily grown its audience, reaching 180 followers as of M12, with continued efforts to expand its influence.
2. **X** (<https://x.com/PLIADESproject>):
 - Primarily used to share quick updates, event announcements, and key achievements.
 - Offers opportunities for real-time engagement with followers through mentions and hashtags.
 - Currently has 38 followers.
3. **YouTube** (<https://www.youtube.com/@PLIADESproject>):
 - Serves as a repository for video content, including project overviews, webinars, and recorded events.
 - Currently hosts two videos, including a general project introduction and a webinar on the International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model.
 - Currently has 21 subscribers.

Performance and Engagement

In the first 12 months of the project:

- The LinkedIn page has produced 24 posts, attracting 415 unique visitors, reaching 15.324 impressions, 564 reactions and 1298 pages views

- The X page has produced 20 posts, recorded over 900 views, with engagement peaks during major events such as webinars and newsletters.
- The YouTube channel has begun building a following, which will grow as additional multimedia content is produced in the coming phases. Currently, it contains two videos with 104 and 83 views.

Figure 9. LinkedIn analytics showing follower growth

Figure 10. LinkedIn analytics showing post interactions

←

PLIADES project

22 posts

Edit profile

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🏢 Researcher 📍 Europe 🔗 pliaDES-project.eu 📅 Joined January 2024

33 Following 37 Followers

Posts
Replies
Highlights
Articles
Media
Likes

PLIADES project @PLIADESproject · Dec 13

📄 📢 The 2nd PLIADES Newsletter is Out! 📄 📢

Don't miss key updates & milestones:

- 🌟 IDS-RAM Webinar insights
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📄 New Publication!

We're excited to announce PLIADES's first [#conference #paper](#):
 "Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not-Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data", presented at the 2024 IEEE IST Conference in Tokyo.

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Figure 11. Views on the PLIADES posts of X

Figure 12. Screenshot of the YouTube channel homepage, showcasing available videos

Next Steps

To further enhance the impact of social media channels, the following actions are planned:

- **Targeted Outreach:** Actively engaging with relevant accounts, groups, and communities to expand the audience base.
- **Video Production:** Developing additional video content to strengthen the YouTube channel and provide dynamic, shareable resources.
- **Analytics Monitoring:** Using platform analytics to refine strategies and optimise post timing, content type, and audience engagement.

Through its growing social media presence, the PLIADES project aims to strengthen its visibility, build connections, and foster active participation from stakeholders across sectors.

2.3.3 Press releases

A first press release was issued, introduced the PLIADES project to the public, detailing its vision, objectives, and consortium members.

Figure 13. First page of the PLIADES launch press release

**AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces
Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability**

types of data to drive innovations in areas such as smart vehicles, predictive maintenance, personalised healthcare services, and more, solving critical problems and improving everyday life.

***Consortium members include:**

Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas CERTH (Greece), 4byDesign Competence Center Private Company (Greece), Atlantis Engineering SA (Greece), Vicomtech (Spain), Eureka (Spain), Energy@Work (Italy), FinEst Centre for Smart Cities, Talltech (Estonia), Innovaia (Spain), Tecnalia (Spain), denn Industrias Pujjaner (Spain), Blue Ocean Robotics (Denmark), Czech Technical University in Prague (Czech Republic), Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt (Germany), ZERO GmbH (Germany), Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (Spain), Mondragon Goi Eskola Politeknikoa Jose Maria Arizmendiarieta, S.Coop (Spain), KU Leuven, Mechatronic System Dynamics (LMSD) research group (Belgium), Ceit - Centro de Estudios e Investigaciones Técnicas (Spain), IDSA - International Data Spaces e.V. (Germany), TNO - Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (Netherlands), CIC bioGUNE - Asociación Centro de Investigación Cooperativa en Biociencias (Spain), BasqueCCAM - Asociación Centro Vasco de Movilidad Conectada, Cooperativa y Autónoma (Spain), AVL List GmbH (Austria), White Research (Brussels), Hypertech S.A. (Greece), Libatton AG (Switzerland), Sipbb - Switzerland Innovation Park Biel/ Bienne AG (Switzerland)

For more information about PLIADES and its ground-breaking initiatives, please visit: <https://www.pliades-project.eu/>

Follow us on X via [@PLIADESproject](#) and on LinkedIn via [pliades-project](#)

Subscribe to our YouTube channel [here](#).

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Page 2

Figure 14. Second page of the PLIADES launch press release, showcasing consortium members and project objectives

The full text of the launch press release is accessible on the project's website at: <https://www.pliades-project.eu/pliades-press-release-2024-05-17-project-overview> .

Next Steps

To ensure continuous visibility and engagement, additional press releases will be issued at critical project milestones. Planned topics include:

- Updates on PLIADES use cases.
- Announcements of significant project results and deliverables.
- Presentation of PLIADES Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- Coverage of major events and participation in conferences.

2.3.4 Newsletters

Newsletters are a vital tool in the PLIADES dissemination strategy, enabling regular communication with stakeholders about the project's progress, activities, and upcoming events. Designed to engage

and inform, these newsletters help maintain a steady connection with the consortium’s network and the broader audience.

Newsletter Strategy

The PLIADES project issues newsletters biannually, ensuring stakeholders are updated on key developments. Each newsletter is distributed via:

- Email campaigns to subscribers using the Mailchimp platform.
- Project website, where newsletters are archived for public access in the Media section (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/media/>).

Figure 15. PLIADES newsletters uploaded on the project web portal upon release

- Social media channels, providing additional outreach and engagement opportunities.

Content Highlights

Newsletter issues may include:

- **Project Updates:** Summaries of recent milestones and achievements.
- **Event Reports:** Coverage of conferences, workshops, and webinars attended by consortium members.
- **Upcoming Activities:** Announcements of planned events, including webinars and demonstrations.

- **Spotlights:** Featured articles on use cases, pilot studies, or partner contributions.

Newsletters Issued

Two issues were published during the first 12 months:

- **Newsletter #1:** Focused on introducing the project, consortium members, and the roadmap for the first year.

[View this email in your browser](#)

NEWSLETTER

ISS. 1 - 2024

Welcome to the PLIADES project

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

Dear reader,

Thank you for subscribing to the PLIADES project newsletter!

PLIADES stands for an advanced AI-enabled framework for Full Data Lifecycles Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration. Our mission is to revolutionise how data is utilised across diverse sectors, from mobility and healthcare to manufacturing and energy. We envision a future where these sectors are seamlessly interconnected, enhancing efficiency and interoperability.

Our goals focus on Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Advanced Driver Assistance and Autonomous Driving (ADAS/AD), and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), supporting advancements in these critical areas.

Since the project's launch, the PLIADES team has been working closely to define the foundational steps for achieving these ambitious goals.

Key Project Information

- Start Date: January 1st, 2024
- End Date: June 30th, 2027 (42 months)
- Important Milestones:
 - 2024: System architecture definition
 - 2026: Preliminary framework deployment and launch of PLIADES data spaces
 - 2027: Pilot testing and evaluation

PLIADES Objectives

The specific objectives of PLIADES include:

- Research and develop novel models, abstractions, and methods for environmentally friendly, context- and human-factors-aware creation of vast amounts of data for mobility, green deal, energy, industrial and healthcare dataspaces.
- Advance data privacy, security, trustworthiness and sovereignty, enabling data owners to safely determine how their information is collected, stored and used.
- Promote advanced data decentralisation and further advance AI-boosted brokers.
- Generate advanced Data Spaces connectors to extend the scope of data spaces interoperability, encompassing full data life cycles into existing data reference architectures.
- Facilitate novel data processing and analytics services to ensure data privacy, trustworthiness, security, resilience, re-use and disposal.
- Deploy the proposed framework in diverse use cases, focusing on transportation, energy, manufacturing, healthcare and green deal sectors.
- Develop new business models that promote data sharing and re-use and establish synergies with other EU initiatives.

[Read more about our goals here](#)

Use Cases of PLIADES

PLIADES outcomes will utilise different types of data spanning six use cases, focusing on diverse dataspace, such as :

- data from smart vehicles to improve their ADAS/AD & CCAM functions and energy management (mobility dataspace),
- patient/doctor HRI data to improve service robots' HRI effectiveness and patient data to improve diagnostic & prognostic clinical models for personalised medicine services (healthcare dataspace),
- manufacturing data to improve zero-waste manufacturing, predictive maintenance and HRI (industrial dataspace).

[Find out more about our use cases](#)

Highlights from the first months

The project is off to an exciting start! Here are some highlights from our initial activities:

[PLIADES Project Launch: Kick-off Meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece](#)

[PLIADES project presented at BDVA and DSSC Workshop on Horizon Europe Projects in Data Life Cycles](#)

[A&R Expo 2024: PLIADES Project Showcased at Industry Event](#)

[Ethics Advisory Board Introduction](#)

[Second Plenary Meeting: Key insights and project updates](#)

[PLIADES Dissemination Material](#)

A brief introduction video of PLIADES

PLIADES Consortium

[Meet the PLIADES partners](#)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135988.

The current newsletter issue reflects only the view of the author(s) and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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The PLIADES Consortium

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- **Newsletter #2:** Provided updates on early project achievements and participations in events.

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NEWSLETTER

ISS. 2 - 2024

Welcome to the PLIADES project

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

Dear reader,

Thank you for subscribing to the PLIADES project newsletter!

Welcome to the second issue of the PLIADES newsletter! As we near the first year of the PLIADES project, we're excited to share the progress we've made and the milestones we've achieved. Over the past few months, our team has been actively driving forward the development of interoperable data spaces and AI-powered solutions, with several significant events and breakthroughs. In this issue, we highlight our recent plenary meeting, key partner activities, insights from major industry events, and innovative research efforts.

Join us as we continue our journey towards shaping the future of data spaces and collaborative innovation.

PLIADES project updates

This section highlights the latest project updates, key events, and activities in which PLIADES has participated:

[Highlights from the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting](#)

[Insights from the PLIADES Webinar on International Data Spaces Reference Architecture \(IDS-RAM\)](#)

[PLIADES at the European Big Data Value Forum \(EBDVF\) 2024](#)

[Atlantis Engineering Showcases PLIADES Innovations](#)

Conference paper

We are thrilled to announce the publication of PLIADES's first conference paper: *"Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not-Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data"*.

This innovative paper, co-authored by **K. Tsiakas, D. Alexiou, D. Giakoumis, A. Gasteratos, and D. Tzovaras**, was presented at the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Imaging Systems and Techniques (IST) in Tokyo, Japan.

[Read more here](#)

New Report: Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces

We are proud to announce the release of an important new report: "Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces" led by DS2 in collaboration with PLIADES, CEDAR, CyclOps and NOUS. This report highlights the outcomes and key insights from the Data Spaces Cluster participation at the Big Data Value Association (BDVA) EBDVF 2024, held in October 2024.

The report reflects the discussions and highlights of the "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks" panel session.

Explore the full report and gain insights into how interoperable data spaces are poised to shape the future of value creation.

ENHANCING VALUE CREATION THROUGH INTEROPERABLE DATA SPACES

Unlock the Power of Data Sharing at EBDVF 2024 - A Post Event Report

November 2024

[Access the report](#)

Webinar on International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference Architecture Model

PLIADES Consortium

[Meet the PLIADES partners](#)

Follow PLIADES in social

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Distribution and Reach

The newsletters have been disseminated to **56 stakeholders** who subscribed through the registration form on the project website. Engagement analytics indicate positive responses, with metrics such as open rates and click-through rates monitored to optimise future issues.

Figure 16. Screenshot of the subscription form available on the PLIADES website

Figure 17. Newsletter #1 distribution and engagement statistics (open rates, clicks) from Mailchimp

Figure 18. Newsletter #2 distribution and engagement statistics (open rates, clicks) from Mailchimp

Next Steps

To maximise the impact of newsletters, the following improvements are planned:

- **Enhanced Visual Appeal:** Incorporating more images, infographics, and video links to make newsletters more engaging.
- **Expanded Subscriber Base:** Actively promoting the subscription option on social media and during project events.

2.3.5 Short videos

Short videos have become a crucial tool for promoting the PLIADES project, helping to make complex concepts accessible to a broader audience while showcasing the project's outcomes and activities. These videos are designed to summarise key project information, making the project more understandable to the public, and to promote its scope, achievements, and ongoing results.

Published Videos

So far, two videos have been produced and shared:

1. Project Overview Video:

- This video, presented during the BDVA-DSSC Workshop organised by the Big Data Value Association and Data Spaces Support Centre, provides a concise introduction to the PLIADES project.
- This short video provides a concise summary of the PLIADES project, outlining its objectives, methodology, and expected outcomes.
- The video is available on the PLIADES YouTube channel (<https://youtu.be/VZzrUJLq3qo>) and has been shared via social media platforms to engage a wider audience.

2. Webinar on International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference Architecture Model (April 2024):

- This video captures the recorded session of the webinar held on 19th April 2024, focusing on the IDS Reference Architecture Model (<https://youtu.be/fiO44bFu1kg>)
- The video offers in-depth insights into the IDS framework and its relevance to the PLIADES project.

Future Video Plans

- **Overview Video:** An introductory video outlining the project's goals, objectives, and expected impacts. This video will serve as a comprehensive introduction to the PLIADES project, providing viewers with a clear understanding of its purpose and scope.
- **Content Demonstrations/Workshops:** Videos showcasing demonstrations and workshops related to the project. These will provide practical insights into the project's applications and methodologies, offering a closer look on the PLIADES project.
- **Promo Video on Use Cases:** Promotional videos focusing on use cases. These will highlight the specific use cases within the PLIADES project, showcasing their progress, challenges and successes to illustrate the project's practical impact.
- **Webinars:** Recorded webinars featuring experts and stakeholders discussing various aspects of the PLIADES project. These webinars will provide in-depth information and facilitate knowledge sharing, addressing both technical and non-technical audiences.
- **Recorded Presentations at Workshops/ Conferences:** Recordings of presentations given at various workshops and conferences. These videos will capture key presentations and insights shared during these events, allowing a broader audience to benefit from the knowledge exchanged.
- **Key Exploitable Results (KERs) Video:** A dedicated video will be created to highlight the KERs of the PLIADES project. This video will focus on the most significant outcomes, demonstrating how these results can be practically applied in various sectors.

2.3.6 Workshops/ Conferences/ Demonstrations

During the first 12 months, the PLIADES project participated in several high-profile events, allowing the consortium to present the project's objectives, progress, and early results to a wider audience. Some of the key events included:

- 1. BDVA-DSSC Workshop (February 2024)**
 - This online workshop, organised by the Big Data Value Association and Data Spaces Support Centre, focused on data spaces, and PLIADES was introduced to relevant stakeholders.
 - Partner: CERTH
- 2. European Robotics Forum (ERF) (March 2024)**
 - Held in Rimini, Italy, this event highlighted PLIADES contributions to automation and robotics.
 - Partner: CERTH, BOR
- 3. Automation and Robotics Expo (April 2024)**
 - Held in Athens, this event highlighted PLIADES' contributions to automation and robotics.
 - Partner: CERTH
- 4. 11th Technology Forum (April 2024)**
 - This international forum in Thessaloniki provided an ideal platform to showcase PLIADES' objectives to a diverse audience.
 - Partner: Atlantis Engineering SA
- 5. First Webinar on IDS Reference Architecture Model (April 2024)**
 - A dedicated webinar focusing on the International Data Spaces (IDS) Reference Architecture Model, aimed at engaging experts and stakeholders.
 - Partner: All consortium partners
- 6. Tech Talk | Aligning international standards for data space interoperability (June 2024)**
 - This online event highlighted PLIADES' approach to data space interoperability.
 - Partner: IDSA
- 7. EUROMAR (Unraveling biological aging) (June-July 2024)**
 - This scientific conference focused on biological aging and showcased PLIADES-related research to an international scientific audience.
 - Partner: CICbioGUNE
- 8. ICSR + BioMed Conference (August 2024)**
 - The conference took place in Singapore
 - Partner: BOR
- 9. Thessaloniki International Fair (September 2024)**
 - Held in Thessaloniki, this event highlighted the goals of PLIADES and inform the public about the contributions of the project and its Use Cases
 - Partner: CERTH
- 10. European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) - Budapest, Hungary (October 2024)**
 - PLIADES was showcased as part of a session on "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks"
 - Partner: AVL
- 11. 17th Maintenance Forum - Athens, Greece (October 2024)**
 - This event provided an opportunity for PLIADES to engage with stakeholders from the manufacturing sector.
 - Partner: Atlantis Engineering SA
- 12. 5th Energia.Tec Exhibition - Athens, Greece (October 2024)**

- PLIADES participated in the exhibition to showcase its contributions to the electromobility sector and entrepreneurs.
- Partner: Atlantis Engineering SA

By participating in these events, PLIADES continues to build a solid network, establish its reputation in the data space and AI sectors, and ensure its findings reach the target audience effectively.

2.3.7 Publications

Scientific publications are a critical element of the PLIADES dissemination strategy, enabling the project to share its findings and innovations with the broader academic, research, and industrial communities. Scientific knowledge generated during the project is already being shared in the following scientific conferences:

Publication type	Title	Authors	Conference	Partner	Date
Paper in proceedings of a conference	Automated data labelling for pedestrian crossing and not-crossing actions using 3D LiDAR and RGB data	K. Tsiakas, D. Alexiou, D. Giakoumis, A. Gasteratos, D. Tzovaras	2024 IEEE International Conference on Imaging Systems & Techniques (IEEE IST 2024), Tokyo, Japan	CERTH	October. 2024

The **public deliverables** will be published on the PLIADES web portal as well as on Zenodo community with open access once they are accepted by the EU.

2.3.8 Zenodo community

The Zenodo community provides an easy-to-use and widely recognised platform for sharing research data, publications, deliverables, software, and multimedia content. It ensures that all PLIADES project materials are stored in a secure, indexed, and accessible way, making it easier for stakeholders to access the latest results, findings, and tools produced throughout the project.

As part of its commitment to open-access dissemination, the PLIADES project has already published a variety of materials on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/pliades-project>). The materials are assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), making them easily discoverable and citable by researchers and stakeholders.

zenodo

Communities
My dashboard
Log in
Sign up

PLIADES project

<https://www.pliades-project.eu/>
Project

New upload

Records Members

6 results found

Sort by Newest

Versions

View all versions

Access status

Open

Resource types

Other

Poster

Presentation

Subjects

AI

Horizon Europe

Innovation

PLIADES

Data Spaces

Brochure

Newsletter

DataSpaces

Flyer

Presentation

File type

PDF

Help

[Search guide](#)

November 29, 2024 (v1)
Other
Open

PLIADES Newsletter #2

Sampatakos, Panagiotis

The first PLIADES newsletter provides updates on early project achievements and participations in events. The newsletter is fully accessible to a broad audience, promoting awareness of the project's goals and activities. PLIADES stands for an advanced AI AI-enabled framework for Full Data...

Part of PLIADES project

Uploaded on December 17, 2024

0 0

November 29, 2024 (v1)
Other
Open

PLIADES Newsletter #1

Sabatakos, Panagiotis

The first PLIADES newsletter provides an engaging introduction to the project, offering insights into its vision, objectives, and expected impact. It highlights PLIADES as an advanced AI-driven framework for Full Data Lifecycle Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration, addressing the growing...

Part of PLIADES project

Uploaded on November 29, 2024

1 2

November 29, 2024 (v1)
Other
Open

PLIADES press release - Project overview

Sabatakos, Panagiotis

The first PLIADES press release introduces the project's vision, objectives, and innovative approach to revolutionising data utilisation across various sectors. It highlights PLIADES as an advanced AI-powered framework designed for Full Data Lifecycle Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration,...

Part of PLIADES project

Uploaded on November 29, 2024

2 2

November 29, 2024 (v1)
Presentation
Open

PLIADES presentation

Sabatakos, Panagiotis

This slide presentation serves as an open dissemination material for the PLIADES project. It is designed to support project partners in sharing the project's vision, objectives, and results, thereby enhancing engagement with stakeholders across the research and business sectors. The...

Part of PLIADES project

Uploaded on November 29, 2024

2 2

November 29, 2024 (v1)
Poster
Open

PLIADES poster

Sabatakos, Panagiotis

This poster serves as an open dissemination material for the PLIADES project. It is designed to support project partners in sharing the project's vision, objectives, and results, thereby enhancing engagement with stakeholders across the research and business sectors. The poster is fully accessible to...

Part of PLIADES project

Uploaded on November 29, 2024

3 3

November 29, 2024 (v1)
Other
Open

PLIADES leaflet

Sabatakos, Panagiotis

This flyer serves as an open dissemination material for the PLIADES project. It is designed to support project partners in sharing the project's vision, objectives, and results, thereby enhancing engagement with stakeholders across the research and business sectors. The flyer is fully accessible to...

Part of PLIADES project

Uploaded on November 29, 2024

5 5

(1)
10 results per page

Figure 19. PLIADES Zenodo community

2.4 Synergies

Synergies play a vital role in maximising the impact and reach of the PLIADES project. By collaborating with other research initiatives, EU-funded projects, and industry partners, PLIADES can amplify its outcomes, share knowledge, and address common challenges in the areas of data spaces, AI integration, and interoperability.

Collaborations with Other EU-funded Projects

Collaborative efforts have been made to establish synergies with other HORIZON-funded projects. These synergies involve exchanging news and social media content, sharing articles for newsletters, and jointly participating in events.

Notably, PLIADES has collaborated with several other projects to form the Data Space Cluster, which includes the following projects:

- **DS2**
- **CEDAR**
- **CyclOps**
- **NOUS**

Throughout the first year of the project, PLIADES has engaged in multiple joint activities with its partner projects, including:

- **Joint Event Participation:**
 - On the 2nd of October 2024, the PLIADES project was showcased at the European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) in Budapest, Hungary. The session titled “Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks” was led by DS2 and featured our partner Bernhard Peischl from AVL, who presented PLIADES alongside the other projects (NOUS, CyclOps, and CEDAR).

- **Co-creation of Dissemination Materials:**
 - The PLIADES project has worked closely with its cluster partners to create joint dissemination materials like the post-event report which encompasses the highlights of the projects' cluster participation at the EBDVF session (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223551>).

3 Performance indicators and monitoring

Monitoring the effectiveness of dissemination and communication activities is crucial to assessing the success of the PLIADES project. By establishing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), the project can measure its progress, identify areas for improvement, and ensure that its communication efforts are aligned with overall objectives.

To track the progress of these KPIs, the PLIADES project uses a combination of analytics tools and regular reports. These include:

- **Website Analytics:** Tools like Google Analytics track visitor data, user interaction, and session duration.
- **Social Media Analytics:** Metrics from LinkedIn, X, and YouTube, such as followers, engagement, and reach.
- **Mailchimp Analytics:** Used for monitoring newsletter distribution and engagement statistics.
- **Event Tracking:** Feedback from events (workshops, conferences) is collected to assess participant satisfaction and engagement.

The table below presents an overview of the dissemination channels and activities defined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D8.1), along with the associated KPIs, target values, and current status. This table serves as a tool for tracking the effectiveness of PLIADES' dissemination strategy, highlighting areas where additional efforts may be necessary to achieve the desired impact.

Dissemination Channels and Activities	KPIs	Targets	Current Status
Project Identity and Branding	Number of branding materials created and distributed.	Logo, colour-space, artboard, graphic visuals	Available online: https://www.pliades-project.eu/media/
Project Website	Website traffic statistics (unique visitors, page views), registrations, blog interactions.	≥700 visits; >120 registrations; ≥150 blog interactions	Website link: https://www.pliades-project.eu Statistics (see section 2.3.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.350 sessions • 781 unique users.
Marketing Pack and Promotional Press Kit	Number of materials created.	Leaflet, poster, slide-presentations, factsheet	Leaflet: See section 2.2.1 Poster: See section 2.2.2 Slide-presentations: See section 2.2.3 Factsheet: planned for the next period
Web/Social Content (Blogposts, Articles, white papers)	Frequency of content posts.	Y1: >1/month	14 blogpost/ articles (https://www.pliades-project.eu/news/)
		Y2: >2/month	-
		Y3: >2/month	-
Social media (LinkedIn, X)	Number of followers, posts, and interactions.	≥200 followers; ≥150 posts; ≥2000 interactions	LinkedIn: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followers: 175 • Posts: 24 posts • Reactions: 564 X: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Followers: 37 • Posts: 20 posts • Views: 900 views
Press Releases, Newsletters, and Digital Briefs	Number of press releases, newsletters, audience reach.	Y1: ≥4	Press releases: 1 Newsletters: 2
		Y2: ≥6	-

		Y3: ≥ 10	-
Videos (YouTube Channel)	Number of videos produced, views, and feedback.	1 promo/pilot/tool; total >10 videos	Planned for the next period
Organisation/ Attendance to Conferences/ Workshops	Number of conferences/workshops organised and attended, number of visitors, and speakers.	Organised: ≥ 2 ; Attended: ≥ 15 ; ≥ 80 visitors; 10 speakers	Attended: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BDVA-DSSC Workshop (February 2024) • European Robotics Forum (ERF) (March 2024) • Automation and Robotics Expo (April 2024) • 11th Technology Forum (April 2024) • First Webinar on IDS Reference Architecture Model (April 2024) • Tech Talk Aligning international standards for data space interoperability (June 2024) • EUROMAR (Unraveling biological aging) (June-July 2024) • ICSR + BioMed Conference (August 2024) • Thessaloniki International Fair (September 2024) • European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) - Budapest, Hungary (October 2024) • 17th Maintenance Forum - Athens, Greece (October 2024) • 5th Energia.Tec Exhibition - Athens, Greece (October 2024) See sections 2.3.6 and 6.4
Open Access Exhibitions and Demonstration Events	Number of exhibitions, demo days, and attendees.	≥ 1 exhibition; ≥ 2 demo days; ≥ 100 attendees	Planned for the next period
Onsite Pilot Promotional Demonstrations/ Workshops	Number of demonstrations and workshops per pilot.	≥ 1 demonstration per pilot; ≥ 2 workshops per pilot	Planned for the next period
Online and/or F2F Training/ Webinars	Number of webinars/trainings and attendees.	≥ 2 webinars/ trainings; ≥ 50 attendees	1 webinar (available online: https://youtu.be/fiO44bFu1kg)
Scientific Publications and Presentations/ Open access reports	Number of journals and conference papers published.	≥ 5 journals; ≥ 15 conference papers	1 conference paper (see section 2.3.7)
Non-Scientific Reports	Number of industry magazine articles.	≥ 1 industry magazine	-
Project Technical e-Publication	Number of downloads.	<25 = poor; 25-75 = good; >75 = excellent	-
Industry Links and Synergies	Number of real market links, adopters, and trials/testers.	≥ 10 real market links; ≥ 5 adopters; ≥ 5 trials/testers	-
F2F with SMEs and Large Industries/ Companies	Number of events and appearances.	≥ 1 event; ≥ 1 appearance	-

To meet these target values, project partners are expected to intensify the communication and dissemination actions in the forthcoming months, putting emphasis on the production of scientific publications, the attendance of external conferences and events as well as the improvement of website visitors and social media followers.

As the project is progressing and generating results, more content is being shared with the public, leading to increased outreach to a wider audience.

4 Training programs initial plan and guidelines

This section aims to outline the development of training programs within the PLIADES project and report the activities of T8.5. The development of a training program on security issues within the scope of the task has two separate goals: a) to effectively train the involved parties on the matter of data security and, b) to promote the project's results to a wider audience.

The training material will be developed during the implementation of the PLIADES platform, aiming to target data security issues emerging from the implementation of the platform's unique components. The best training method will be decided based on the outcomes of the training program that will be tested with the help of end-users inside the consortium.

4.1 Background and training needs

Data security refers to the protection of digital information throughout its entire life cycle, from actions like unauthorized access, corruption or theft^{2,3}. The term refers to hardware, software, storage and user devices, access and administrative controls, as well as organisations policies and procedures.

Within PLIADES, the protection of data involves many aspects such: privacy, security, trustworthiness, and sovereignty. One of the project's key objectives is to advance data protection with its technological competences while complying with international data security standards (ISO/IEC 27001:2022, ISO/IEC 27701:2019 and GDPR provisions). Data security will be ensured during the integration of multiple dataspace and while maintaining interoperability within and between different sectors.

A system that fulfils the requirements of ISO/IEC 27001 preserves CIA: Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability of information. *Confidentiality* means that only the right people can access information held by a specific organisation. *Information Integrity* refers to the organisation's data that needs to be safely stored and not erased or damaged. *Availability of data* means that an organisation and its clients can access the information whenever necessary so that business purposes and customer expectations are satisfied⁴.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) refers to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. This regulation proposed by the EU respects all the fundamental rights and freedoms and addresses the rapid technological developments, which further facilitate the free flow of personal data, while ensuring a high level of the protection of personal data⁵.

Under this scope, and when working on the aforementioned technical developments, training of the involved partners into the emerging issues of data security deems of high importance. New concepts like data ownership, traceability, usage policies related to data and cybersecurity guidelines are expected to be introduced in order to enhance awareness and data sovereignty.

Some of the technical tasks that are related to the data security issues, and showcase the need for data security awareness are the following:

² Fortinet. (2024). *Data Security: Definition, Importance, and Types*. Fortinet.
<https://www.fortinet.com/resources/cyberglossary/data-security>

³ IBM. (2021). *What is data security? Definition, solutions and how to secure data*. IBM.
<https://www.ibm.com/topics/data-security>

⁴ ISO. (2022). *ISO/IEC 27001 standard – information security management systems*. ISO.
<https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

⁵ The European Parliament and The Council of The European Union. (2016). *General Data Protection Regulation*.
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

T2.1 “Analysis of SoA, current data spaces architectures and extensions requirements”

T3.7 “Quality and Legislation compliance-aware cross-domain data governance”

T4.2 “De-centralization strategies for cloud to edge to IoT data transfer”

T4.3 “Privacy-preserving data sharing and analysis techniques for collaborative intelligence in mobility and autonomous vehicles data spaces”

T4.5 “Data security across multiple integrated data spaces”

T4.7 “Personal Data flows Mapping and GDPR”

T5.6 “AI-boosted connectors for data transformation, secure and privacy-preserving data sharing

Also, based on research data, in March 2024 the number of 102,499,341 records breached, showcasing an increasing number of cyberattacks⁶. Some of the most targeted sectors are public data, IT services and software, manufacturing, energy and healthcare⁷. All the above points will be taken into account when developing the PLIADES training content.

4.2 Available training methods

There are several types of training methods available, all aiming to maximize the impact of the shared information in the most comfortable way and by fitting the trainee’s schedule at the same time. Some of the most spread and used training methods that could be applicable to the PLIADES training program and able to serve its goals are listed below.

Case Studies

The case study method is using real life or imaginary scenarios to learn skills in a practical way⁸. The trainee practices their analytical skills, they are expressing arguments and participating in group discussions in attempt to provide with the optimal solution for each of the presented cases. It can be great for focused topics, but not for very complex ones.

Instructor-Led Training

The basic characteristic of Instructor-Led Training is that an instructor leads and facilitates the training procedure for the participants. A presentation in the form of a lecture could be used, and the training can be both in person and online. This type of training offers real time interaction, but it allows for interactive discussions, and it can answer questions that were not covered in real-time. This training method allows for personalised instructions and collaboration opportunities between the participants. One disadvantage of this training method might be that learners cannot follow their own pace, since usually there are multiple people involved.

Online Training (live or asynchronous)

⁶ Kosling, K. (2024, April 18). *Data Breaches and Cyber Attacks in Europe in March 2024 – 102,499,341 Records Breached*. IT Governance Blog En. <https://www.itgovernance.eu/blog/en/data-breaches-and-cyber-attacks-in-europe-in-march-2024-102499341-records-breached>

⁷ IT Governance Europe. (2024, June 19). *Data Breaches and Cyber Attacks – Europe 2024 Report - IT Governance Blog En*. IT Governance Blog En. <https://www.itgovernance.eu/blog/en/data-breaches-and-cyber-attacks-in-2024-in-europe#monthly-trends>

⁸ Hammond, J. S. (2002, April 16). *Learning by the Case Method* [Review of *Learning by the Case Method*].

Harvard Business School.

https://projects.ig.harvard.edu/files/sdpfellowship/files/hbs_casemethod_overview.pdf#:~:text=In%20short%2C%20the%20case%20method%20is%20really%20a,for%20each%20case%20are%20provided%20in%20the%20schedule%29

Online training is a computer-based method and can be delivered from a distance. Online training can be either live or asynchronous, depending on the training needs. Each training method has different requirements. For example, live training requires instructors. This training method allows instructors and users to interact with each other and the learning takes place in real time. Asynchronous training allows trainees to learn at their own pace, as no real-time interaction takes place. However, it is a requirement that all the training content is created in advance, alongside self-evaluation material, quizzes and interactive activities⁹.

Advantages of live training, including amongst others, are the increase of completion rate and motivation to learn, while participants can interact with the instructors and provide feedback in real time. Asynchronous training often is more practical, as trainees can adopt and learn at their own pace and during their preferred timing, allowing for more flexibility¹⁰. A form of asynchronous training is the video-based training using pre-recorded material.

Gamification

Gamification as a training method combines elements of games with learning material. The learning objectives are communicated through an interactive experience and realistic applications. It often involves rewards like points and level increases, encouraging trainees to participate more actively in the learning process, and retain the information more easily over time.

On-the-job training (Hands-on training)

This type of training usually focuses on the practical skills required for a specific job, therefore a trainee learns by executing related tasks at work. As a training method is more focused on unique needs and it requires extra time. In a business environment, it can take the form of an internship, for example. It results quickly because it is closely related to individual skills and personal growth.

Coaching (Mentoring)

This training method shares similarities with the hands-on-training. However, it creates a relationship between the trainee and a more experienced professional, allowing for more specific questions and guidance. As a method of training can be more inspiring and can be executed both virtually and in-person.

Handbook

A handbook is a training manual that can act as a step-by step guide that helps the trainee at every step of a specific procedure. It is a complete document that can include introductions, specific units for the learning objectives and answers to commonly asked questions. The structure of the document can easily direct the trainees to search for information.

4.3 Training Program Development Methodology

For the development of the training program, an initial plan of five separate steps has been designed, specifying an indicative timeline for each stage. The individual steps are described in the sections below.

The steps of the plan as well as distinct steps and proposed timelines are presented in Figure 1:

⁹ Gore, E. (2023, February 9). *7 Types of Training Methods (and How to Choose)*. ELM Learning. <https://elmlearning.com/blog/training-methods/>

¹⁰ *Synchronous vs Asynchronous Training: Differences, Pros, Cons, and How-To Host Each*. (n.d.). Team Building Hub. <https://teambuildinghub.com/team-building/virtual/managing-team-development/training/synchronous-vs-asynchronous/>

Figure 20: Training Program Development Proposed Methodology and timeline

4.3.1 Stage 1: Desk research, specification of the training context

Upon the initial stage, it is important to specify specific training topics and target audiences for the PLIADES training program. During this phase, desk research will take place to identify current trends, data security standards and regulations that could be related to the implementation of PLIADES and therefore, would be points of interest for the stakeholders involved.

During the first stage, the target audience for the PLIADES training content will be selected amongst the PLIADES consortium, targeting the participants of the PLIADES ecosystem (data consumers and data providers). Afterwards, the training program is expected to be disseminated to all the dissemination targets as well, familiarizing the wider audience with the solutions proposed by PLIADES. Dataspace ecosystem stakeholders, key actors of the mobility, energy, healthcare, industry and the Green Deal sector will be approached in order to experience the benefits proposed on the matter of data security.

4.3.2 Stage 2: Survey targeting the internal stakeholders

During the second stage of the design of the training program, a survey will be conducted to identify areas of interest and training needs on the matter of data security amongst the consortium partners. The survey will contain a few infographic questions to identify the roles of the partners contributing to it and their corresponding training needs, the subjects they wish to be trained in, and their desired method of training.

The processed results of the survey will facilitate the creation of specific content for the first version of the training module, based on preferences, what can be available and what can be publicly shared, as the training content will be part of the dissemination results and will be shared amongst potential users of the PLIADES framework.

A preview of the survey can be found in Table 2:

Table 2. Preview of the survey on the training content that will be shared with the partners

#	Question
A. Infographics	
Q1	What is your organisation name?
Q2	What is your organisation type? <i>i. SME, ii. RTO, iii. Large Company, Enterprise, iv. Other</i>
Q3	What is your role in the PLIADES project? <i>i. Technology Provider, ii. End user, iii. Other, please specify</i>
Q4	In which WPs are you involved in? <i>i. WP1, ii. WP2,....,viii. WP8</i>
Q5	Are you a KER owner or contributor? <i>i. Yes, ii. No</i>
Q6	What type of licensing do you plan to use for your developments? <i>i. Propetary, ii. Open Source, iii.etc</i>
B. Training Material	
Q7	What are the data security issues that you would like to be trained on? Please rate them according to priority <i>i. GDPR, ii. AI regulations iii. CIA (Confidentiality, integrity, availability), iv. Other</i>
Q8	Do you have internal training needs on data security issues as an organisation? <i>i. Yes, ii. No, Please specify</i>
Q9	Is there already training material available on data security within your organisation? <i>i. Yes, ii. No, Please specify</i>
Q10	Would you be in the position to provide data security know-how? <i>i. Yes, ii. No</i>
Q11	Which method would you prefer for your training? <i>i. Online live course ii. Online pre-recorded training material iii. Handbook iv. Available on Public Portals (Zenodo, Open AIRE) v. Hands on training</i>
Q12	How much time do you have available for training per month (approximately)? Please, specify.

4.3.3 1st version of the training program

The 1st version of the PLIADES training program will be designed based on the specific training needs related to the subject of data security identified during the previous stage. Results of the survey and the desk research will be used for that purpose.

The material for the training program will be created by using inputs from the task's participants and perhaps technical partners of interest contributing with material from software modules related to data security (e.g. the AI-Connector, compliant with IDS standards).

This training material will be connected with the project results, so that it can act as dissemination material as well, providing insights to the PLIADES achievements in the topic of data security.

4.3.4 Validation within the consortium

The 1st version of the training program is expected to be validated within the consortium with tools like online surveys, webinars or face to face sessions. The content of the training module, as well as the selected method of training, will be tested and evaluated by internal partners at first, so that the final module will be fully ready to be shared with external end users to promote the project's results and platform's usage. Selected software implementations should be mature enough during these demonstrations, so the period foreseen validation is from M37 to M40.

The overall goal of the training content will be to empower individuals and organisations to make informed decisions about their data, and ensure privacy and security are always protected.

4.3.5 Iterations and final release

Comments and feedback gathered during the validation period will be used to update and improve the training module before final release. The comments will be collected via training sessions that will be held synchronous or asynchronous and with evaluation surveys, to make sure that specific recommendations will be gathered. Follow-up questions, e-mails or interviews might take place to help identify areas of improvement of the training content, and parts that might not be clear enough to the end-users.

The final and improved version of the training program is expected to be ready by M42 as a project result. During the final stage, and the release of the final version, there will be some additional key issues that need to be addressed. One is the dissemination level of the final training material and subsequently the place where it would be available (e.g. the project's website). For confidential information, an idea would be to split the training content so that there are private and public parts. The private parts can become available to specific stakeholders that fulfil predefined conditions (for example pay a fee for the PLIADES solution). These issues will become clearer as the initial version of the training material is produced, as it highly depends on its content.

5 Conclusions

The PLIADES project has made significant strides in its dissemination and communication activities during its first year. The project's efforts to raise awareness, engage stakeholders, and share its initial steps through various channels have proven successful in fostering visibility and participation. By leveraging tools such as the project website, social media, newsletters, and events participation, PLIADES has effectively communicated its objectives and progress to a wide audience, including researchers, industry professionals, and the public.

Monitoring the performance indicators has provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of these activities, enabling the project to measure its impact and adjust strategies where necessary. While progress has been positive, ongoing efforts are required to further expand the reach of the project, particularly in increasing website traffic, engaging more stakeholders through social media, and ensuring widespread visibility of the project's key results.

The development of PLIADES training content will act as another aspect of the project's dissemination activities. The PLIADES training program will be fully completed towards the end of the project and will be dedicated on multiple security issues that arise from the project's achievements but are also relative to the overall information flow technological challenges.

Looking ahead, the next iteration of this report, "D8.3: Dissemination and Communication Activities Report (v2)", to be prepared at the end of the second year of the project, will present the cumulative impact of the PLIADES project, reflecting the continued progress and achievements across its dissemination and communication efforts. Moreover, it will include the updates that have taken place regarding the training material objectives, target audiences and selected training methods. Further updates to the training plan might also be presented, based on the workflow progress and research findings.

6 Appendix

6.1 Deliverable template

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135988

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

Project acronym:	PLIADES
Project name:	AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability
Grant Agreement No:	101135988
Call:	HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01-02
Type of action:	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Start of project:	01/01/2024

Deliverable

Deliverable title

Work Package:	
Task:	
Lead Beneficiary:	
Due Date:	
Submission Date:	
Deliverable Status:	
Deliverable Type:	
Dissemination Level:	

GA #101135988

Authors

Surname	First Name	Beneficiary

Reviewers

Surname	First Name	Beneficiary

Version History

Version	Date	Modifications made by

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6.2 Presentation template

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

Speaker's name

Speakers' organisation

Date and place

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135988

Click to add title

- Edit Master text styles

Footer

2

Thank you for your attention!

Any Questions?

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[pliaDES-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/pliaDES-project)

6.3 Newsletter template

NEWSLETTER

ISS. 1 - 2024

Dear reader,
Thank you for subscribing to the PLIADES project newsletter!

About PLIADES

PLIADES stands for an advanced AI-enabled framework for Full Data Lifecycles Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration. Our mission is to revolutionise how data is utilised across diverse sectors, from mobility and healthcare to manufacturing and energy. We envision a future where these sectors are seamlessly interconnected, enhancing efficiency and interoperability.

News item 1

Our goals focus on Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Advanced Driver Assistance and Autonomous Driving (ADAS/AD), and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), supporting advancements in these critical areas.

Since the project's launch, the PLIADES team has been working closely to define the foundational steps for achieving these ambitious goals.

Key Project Information

- Start Date: January 1st, 2024
- End Date: June 30th, 2027 (42 months)
- Important Milestones
 - 2024: System architecture definition
 - 2026: Preliminary framework deployment and launch of PLIADES data spaces
 - 2027: Pilot testing and evaluation

News item 2

Highlights from the first months

The project is off to an exciting start! Here are some highlights from our initial activities:

Highlights section

PLIADES Project Launch: Kick-off Meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece

PLIADES project presented at BDVA and DSSC Workshop on Horizon Europe Projects in Data Life Cycles

A brief introduction video of PLIADES

Multimedia/ video section

Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis
Project Coordinator
Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH)

 News/
activities
section

PLIADES Consortium

Meet the PLIADES partners

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135988.

The current newsletter issue reflects only the view of the author(s) and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Follow PLIADES in social

Thank you for being part of the PLIADES journey!
The PLIADES Consortium

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Newsletter footer

6.4 List of dissemination activities

No	Type of activities	Partners Involved	Title	Date	Place	Type of Audience ('multiple choices' is possible)	Size of audience	Countries addressed	Web links
1	Web	Hypertech	PLIADESproject started! Kick-off meeting of @HorizonEU @PLIADESproject at @CERTHell	17/1/2024	X	Followers & visitors	56 views		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1747682297703190705
2	Web	Hypertech	In a dynamic two-day kick-off meeting at Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) on 17-18/01, the PLIADES project had a fantastic start! 🚀 Exciting times ahead! 🌍 #PLIADES #ResearchProgress #HorizonEurope #research and #innovation programme	19/1/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 768, Clicks: 190, Click through rate (CTR): 24,74%, Likes: 26, Comments: 1, Reposts: 5, Engagement rate: 28,91%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7154108305290801155
3	Web	Hypertech	Exploring Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) facilities, guided by Dimitris Giakoumis and Andreas Kargakos in the context of the kick-off meeting of PLIADES project 🚀 #PLIADESKickOff #researchexcellence	19/1/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 3074, Clicks: 757, Click through rate (CTR): 24,63%, Likes: 62, Comments: 1, Reposts: 7, Engagement rate: 26,90%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7154128802573410305
4	Web	Hypertech	In a dynamic two-day kick-off meeting at @CERTHell on 17-18/01, the PLIADES project had a fantastic start! 🚀 Exciting times ahead! 🌍 #PLIADES #ResearchProgress	19/1/2024	X	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 447, Clicks: 42, Click through rate (CTR): 9,40%, Likes: 22, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 15,21%		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1748343681101213967
5	Web	Hypertech	🚀 Exciting news! #PLIADES project showcased at the recent workshop	21/1/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 447, Clicks:		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7166046219369234434

			<p>organised by the BDVA - Big Data Value Association and the Data Spaces Support Centre focusing on Horizon Europe Projects in Data Life Cycles. Dr. Dimitris Giakoumis, our Coordinator from Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH), had the honour of presenting our project's mission and objectives to a diverse audience, including members of BDVA's Task Force on Data Spaces and representatives from DSSC.</p> <p>This event provided a crucial platform for us and four other Horizon Europe projects to discuss our goals and anticipated impacts, particularly regarding Data Sharing in the Common EU Data Spaces.</p> <p>Stay tuned for more updates on our journey!</p> <p>Check more out more: https://lnkd.in/dVXRrF2C</p>				42, Click through rate (CTR): 9,40%, Likes: 22, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 15,21%		
6	Web	White Research	Article on WR's website for PLIADES project	February 2024	Online	Website's visitors	Impressions: 411, Clicks: 20, Click through rate (CTR): 4,87%,	Likes:11, Comments: 0,Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 7,79%	https://white-research.eu/portfolio/pliades-ai-enabled-data-lifecycles-optimization-and-data-spaces-integration-for-increased-efficiency-and-interoperability/
7	Web	White Research	Social media post on WR's account about the Kick off meeting held in Thessaloniki	February 2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 1080, Clicks: 369, Click through rate (CTR): 34,17%, Likes: 38, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 38,06%		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/white-research-sprl_ai-efficiency-security-activity-7155880751815667712-YzEA?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
8	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES Project Launch: Kick-off Meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece	7/2/2024	Online	Website's visitors	43 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/02/07/pliades-project-launch-kick-off-meeting-in-thessaloniki-greece/

9	Web	White Research	Mention of Kick-off of the PLIADES project meeting in the January edition of White Research Journal	9/2/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 547, Clicks: 25, Click through rate (CTR): 4,57%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 8,59%		https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/welcome-january-edition-our-company-newsletter-white-research-sprl-iglof/?trackingId=fS2RTDaS2S8HzkBukeCzDg%3D%3D
10	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES project presented at BDVA and DSSC Workshop on Horizon Europe Projects in Data Life Cycles	21/2/2024	Online	Website's visitors	53 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/02/21/pliades-project-bdva-dssc-workshop/
11	Web	Hypertech	🚀 Exciting news! #PLIADES showcased at @BDVA_EU and DSSC Workshop on Horizon Europe Projects in #DataLifeCycles. Our coordinator, Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis highlighted our commitment to advancing European data strategies. #HorizonEurope Learn more: https://t.co/q1ckX35nKj	21/2/2024	X	Followers & visitors	62 views		https://x.com/PLIADEsproject/status/1760278496738148496
12	Videos	CERTH	European Robotics Forum, Project Overview	March 2024	Rimini, Italy	Scientific, industry		EU	https://youtu.be/VZzrUJLq3qo
13	Conferences	BOR	European Robotics Forum	March 2024	Rimini, Italy	Scientific, industry	20	European countries	
14	Web	Hypertech	🚀 Exciting News from A&R Expo 2024! 📺 The recent Automation & Robotics Expo in Athens from April 12th to 14th, 2024, showcased the latest innovations in the field. Among the 120+ exhibitors was the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH), proudly presenting PLIADES' vision and objectives. For more information, check here: https://lnkd.in/d/JttaiG	23/4/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 288, Clicks: 28, Click through rate (CTR): 9,72%, Likes:12, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 14,24%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7188520794107297792
15	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES at the A&R Expo 2024	23/4/2024	Online	Website's visitors	41 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/04/23/pliades-a-r-expo-2024/
16	Conferences	Atlantis Engineering SA	11th Technology Forum	25/4/2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	Industry, Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Innovators	100 (approx.)	International event	https://technology-forum.eu/

17	Web	Hypertech	Exciting News from A&R Expo 2024! @CERTHellas proudly showcasing #PLIADES' vision and objectives in the recent Automation & Robotics Expo in Athens from April 12th to 14th, 2024 Show more here: https://t.co/Br1F3zQaNI	30/4/2024	X	Followers & visitors	42 views	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1785279115601289345
18	Web	White Research	Social media post on WR's account about the 2nd project meeting held in Bilbao	May 2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	538	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/white-research-sprl_the-pliers-project-recently-gathered-activity-7207314221481549825-V4fM?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
19	Web	Hypertech	 Read the press release here: https://lnkd.in/dAXBCdhj #PressRelease #Innovation #Research #Collaboration	17/5/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 411, Clicks: 20, Click through rate (CTR): 4,87%, Likes:11, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 7,79%	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7197245987801698304
20	Web	Hypertech	Revolutionising Data Utilisation Across Sectors	17/5/2024	Online	Website's visitors	32 views	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/05/17/the-pliers-project/
21	Web	Hypertech	Exciting News! The first press release for the #PLIADESproject is now available on our website! Read it here: https://t.co/TVL9I4ZYg6	17/5/2024	X	Followers & visitors	44 views	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1791480938838307320
22	Web	Hypertech	 https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq #PLIADESproject #Innovation #Research #Collaboration #HorizonEurope #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration	29/5/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 1080, Clicks: 369, Click through rate (CTR): 34,17%, Likes: 38, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 38,06%	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201565063126618113
23	Web	Hypertech	The #PLIADES team is meeting today at the AIC - Automotive Intelligence Center to discuss our project progress. Stay tuned for updates on our achievements and outcomes and don't forget to visit our	29/5/2024	X	Followers & visitors	185 views	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1795814735608418586

			website for more ↗ https://pliades-project.eu						
24	Web	Hypertech	<p>📌 The second day of the PLIADES project is still in progress! Big thanks to Innovalia Association for the fantastic hosting at the AIC-Automotive Intelligence Center. #Innovation #Collaboration #PLIADESproject #Innovation #Research #Collaboration #HorizonEurope #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration</p>	30/5/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 937, Clicks: 352, Click through rate (CTR): 37,57%, Likes: 43, Comments: 0, Reposts: 4, Engagement rate: 42,58%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201920999854862336
25	Web	Hypertech	<p>📌 The second day of the PLIADES project is still in progress! Thanks to @Innovalia_group for the fantastic hosting at the AIC-Automotive Intelligence Center.</p>	30/5/2024	X	Followers & visitors	56 views		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1796155637786648695
26	Web	Hypertech	<p>📌 Exciting News! 📌 We are introducing the Ethics Advisory Board of the #PLIADES project! This dedicated team will ensure that our R&D activities uphold the highest ethical standards.</p> <p>👥 Meet our esteemed members: Gabriela B., Javier Del Ser, Andrej Pastorek, Prof. Ondrej Pribyl, Jesus M. Santamaria and sofia segkouli.</p> <p>Their expertise is pivotal to our success and ethical integrity.</p> <p>🔗 Learn more: https://lnkd.in/dmrbw-tT</p> <p>#Ethics #HorizonEurope #Innovation #AI #DataProtection #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration</p>	7/6/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 547, Clicks: 25, Click through rate (CTR): 4,57%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 8,59%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7204774947053907968
27	Web	Hypertech	Introducing the PLIADES project's Ethics Advisory Board	7/6/2024	Online	Website's visitors	44 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/06/11/second-plenary-meeting-of-the-pliades-project-key-highlights-and-progress/

28	Web	Hypertech	Meet our experts https://t.co/oPgD0rmcd5	7/6/2024	X	Followers & visitors	44 views		https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1799009937429078121
29	Web	Hypertech	Stay updated: https://lnkd.in/dPyM3rjy #PLIADES #HorizonEurope #Innovation #AI #DataInnovation #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration	11/6/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 961, Clicks: 67, Click through rate (CTR): 6,97%, Likes: 26, Comments: 0, Reposts: 5, Engagement rate: 10,20%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206210971621634048
30	Web	Hypertech	Second Plenary Meeting of the PLIADES Project: Key Highlights and Progress	11/6/2024	Online	Website's visitors	80 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/06/11/second-plenary-meeting-of-the-pliades-project-key-highlights-and-progress/
31	Web	Hypertech	Stay updated: https://t.co/9QhMq5JOfL	11/6/2024	X	Followers & visitors	93 views		https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1800447630168011014
32	Posters	CICbioGUNE	Unraveling biological aging: machine learning models for identifying age-related metabolic deterioration from NMR serum data	30 June – 4 July 2024	EUROMAR. Bilbao	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	700	International (~100)	
33	Web	White Research	Mention of 2nd PLIADES project meeting in the summer edition of White Research Journal	31/7/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	576		https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/white-research-journal-summer-2024-edition-white-research-sprl-nlvhf/?trackingId=RM3nPGVkrZOnTkTgi5rGuQ%3D%3D
34	Conferences	BOR	ICSR + BioMed	August 2024	Singapore	Scientific	40	Singapore, China	
35	Other	IDSA	Tech Talk Aligning international standards for data space interoperability	13/6/2024	Online	Research, Scientific, Industry	40	International event	
36	Fair	CERTH	Thessaloniki International Fair	07-15/6/2024	Thessaloniki, Greece	Industry, Researchers,			

						Entrepreneurs, Innovators			
37	Web	Hypertech	<p>✦ Excited to announce that PLIADES with Bernhard Peischl (AVL) will join @DS2_EU 's session with @nous_project, @CyclopsProject & @cedar_eu at @BDVA_eu 2024!</p> <p>Topic: Interoperability of data spaces for seamless value creation</p>	1/10/2024	X	Followers & visitors	38 views		https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1841143355675160986
38	Web	Hypertech	<p>✦ We are excited to announce that PLIADES project, with Bernhard Peischl from AVL, will be participating in the joint session led by DS2, alongside our sister projects NOUS, CyclopsProject and CEDAR EU at this year's BDVA - Big Data Value Association #EBDVF2024!</p> <p>Interoperability of data spaces for seamless value creation networks</p> <p>📅 2 October 🕒 10 AM CET 📍 Budapest, Hungary</p> <p>Learn more about the session 📄 https://lnkd.in/dKRpSi64</p>	1/10/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 451, Clicks: 24, Click through rate (CTR): 5,32%, Likes: 15, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 8,87%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7246908755597049856
39	Web	Hypertech	<p>Unlock the Power of Data Sharing at EBDVF 2024: Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces</p>	1/10/2024	Online	Website's visitors	25 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/10/01/ebdvf-2024/
40	Presentations; Conferences	AVL	<p>Session title: "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks", European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)</p>	2/10/2024	Budapest, Hungary	Industry; Researchers; Innovators; Policy makers		EU	
41	Conferences	Atlantis Engineering SA	<p>17th Maintenance Forum</p>	10/10/2024	Athens, Greece	Industry	150	Greece, EU	https://www.maintenance-forum.gr/
42	Exhibitions	Atlantis Engineering SA	<p>5th Energia.Tec</p>	11-13/10/2024	Athens, Greece	Industry	300	Greece, EU	https://www.energia-tec.gr/en/
43	Web	Hypertech	<p>🚀 Our session on "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks" at #EBDVF24 was a huge success! @BernhardPeischl from AVL presented #PLIADES alongside</p>	23/10/2024	X	Followers & visitors	68 views		https://x.com/PLIADESPROJECT/status/1849053168388182194

			@DS2_EU, @nous_project, @CyclopsProject & @cedar_eu. Learn more at https://pliaDES-project.eu/news/					
44	Web	Hypertech	Missed it? Watch the full recording here: https://lnkd.in/d/J9DdiXt #IDS #IDA_RAM #DataSpaces #DigitalTransformation #PLIADES #Interoperability #webinar #IDSA	23/10/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 298, Clicks: 17, Click through rate (CTR): 5,70%, Likes: 14, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 10,74%	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7257343445332058112
45	Web	Hypertech	On the 2nd of October, Bernhard Peischl from AVL proudly represented the PLIADES project at this significant event in Budapest. The session, led by DS2 and attended by our sister projects: NOUS, CyclopsProject and CEDAR EU, delved deep into critical topics like data lifecycle management, AI-driven services and human-centred integration within data spaces We explored how data interoperability can drive value creation across sectors, helping unlock new opportunities for businesses and society. Want to know more about the outcomes? Visit https://lnkd.in/d/GKaQesq for updates! #DataSpaces #Interoperability #AI #BigData #Innovation #EBDVF2024	23/10/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 625, Clicks: 146, Click through rate (CTR): 23,36%, Likes: 29, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 28,32%	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254816772254539778
46	Web	Hypertech	Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks – A Great Success at EBDVF 2024!	23/10/2024	Online	Website's visitors	23 views	https://www.pliaDES-project.eu/2024/10/23/ebdvf-2024-avl/

47	Web	Hypertech	#Webinar Highlight: Learn all about the #IDS Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) and data space protocols from the event organised by #IDSA as part of the #PLIADES project! Watch the full recording on YouTube: Watch here https://youtube.com/watch?v=fiO44bFu1kg	30/10/2024	X	Followers & visitors	32 views	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1851579474510283105
48	Web	Hypertech	Insights from the PLIADES Webinar on International Data Spaces Reference Architecture (IDS-RAM)	30/10/2024	Online	Website's visitors	30 views	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/10/30/ids-ram-webinar/
49	Web	Hypertech	The #PLIADES team is gearing up for the 3rd Plenary Meeting in Graz, Austria AT from Nov 19-21! We're excited to drive forward #DataSpaces & #AI innovations with sessions, updates, and our WP4 Hackathon for hands-on, collaborative solutions! https://t.co/RnE4DQkFU0	14/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	36 views	https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1857033449502126309
50	Web	Hypertech	Key Event: The WP4 Hackathon will give attendees a hands-on experience with the systems PLIADES is developing. Participants will work in mixed remote and on-site teams to brainstorm solutions, focusing on IDS RAM and connector development. https://lnkd.in/d_VwmTKu #PLIADESProject #DataSpaces #AI #DataInnovation #GrazMeeting #DataLifeCycles #DataIntegration #HorizonEurope	14/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 370, Clicks: 19, Click through rate (CTR): 5,14%, Likes: 17, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 10,00%	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7262798525460062210
51	Web	Hypertech	Countdown to the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting in Graz	14/11/2024	Online	Website's visitors	17 views	https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/11/14/3rd-plenary-announcement-graz/

			<p> Not subscribed? Sign up at https://pliades-project.eu</p>						
52	Web	Hypertech	<p>#HorizonEurope</p>	15/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	13 views		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/185736942272737004
			<p> Sign up in moments: Scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter: https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq</p> <p>#PLIADESProject #HorizonEurope #AI #DataSpaces #Innovation #Newsletter</p>					Impressions: 427, Clicks: 26, Click through rate (CTR): 6,09%, Likes: 18, Comments: 0, Reposts: 3, Engagement rate: 11,01%	
53	Web	Hypertech		15/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors			https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7263133975429201920
			<p> Day 1 of the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting in Graz!</p> <p>Hosted by AVL, we kicked off with progress reviews across WPs and launched the #Hackathon session, fostering collaboration</p>						
54	Web	Hypertech		19/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	21 views		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1858882620446089661

			on IDS RAM and connector development. 📍 Stay tuned for more updates! 🌟 🔗 https://pliades-project.eu/news/						
55	Web	Hypertech	📣 Day 1 of the 3rd PLIADES project Plenary Meeting in Graz! Hosted by AVL, today marked an energetic start to our meeting as we delved into detailed discussions and updates, approaching the end of the project's first year. 🌟 🔍 Key Highlights: • Progress reviews across several Work Packages (WPs), ensuring alignment with our goals. • The much-anticipated #Hackathon Session is now underway, uniting remote and on-site participants to collaborate on IDS RAM and connector development- a true testament to innovation and teamwork! With an excellent start, we're looking forward to more engaging discussions and activities in the coming days! 📍 📧 Subscribe to our newsletter to stay in the loop & receive all the latest updates, event news, and opportunities to be involved. Scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter: https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq #PLIADESProject #DataSpaces #AI #Collaboration #Innovation	19/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 1483, Clicks: 343, Click through rate (CTR): 23,13%, Likes: 57, Comments: 0, Reposts: 8, Engagement rate: 27,51%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264647133859901441
56	Web	Hypertech	📣 Day 2 of the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting - Building on Progress and Exploring Innovations! The second day of our meeting continues with an engaging agenda, focusing on technical advancements and collaboration. This morning, we delved deep into WP4:	20/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 1416, Clicks: 388, Click through rate (CTR): 27,40%, Likes: 46, Comments:		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264976290858876929

			<p>Green and Decentralized Data Storage and Security, with detailed updates on WP tasks. 🌍🔒</p> <p>We also reviewed WP8: Dissemination, Exploitation, and Standardization, highlighting progress on dissemination activities, the exploitation plan, and training programs - key steps toward impactful outcomes. 🌟</p> <p>📅 The program now shifts to Technical Workshops, exploring our innovative Use Cases.</p> <p>As we wrap up the day, we eagerly await the exciting visit to AVL premises for an immersive look into their state-of-the-art facilities. 🚀</p> <p>The momentum continues as the PLIADES project moves towards its vision of advancing data spaces, AI, and green solutions!</p> <p>#PLIADESProject #DataSpaces #AI #Collaboration #Innovation #HorizonEurope</p> <p>DS2 NOUS CEDAR EU CyclopsProject</p>				0, Reposts: 8, Engagement rate: 31,21%		
57	Web	Hypertech	<p>🚀 A dynamic period for the PLIADES project! ATLANTIS Engineering SA proudly represented PLIADES innovations at both the 17th Maintenance Forum and the 5th Energia.Tec exhibition.</p> <p>At the Maintenance Forum, Atlantis showcased PLIADES' AI solutions that enhance interoperability across diverse dataspace. Meanwhile, at Energia.Tec, Atlantis showcased PLIADES cutting-edge advancements in dataspace technology.</p> <p>Read more: https://lnkd.in/d7CcNt4U</p> <p>More to come as we lead the way in data-</p>	25/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 262, Clicks: 28, Click through rate (CTR): 10,69%, Likes: 21, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 19,47%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7266794234584682497

			driven solutions! #PLIADESproject #Innovation #Dataspaces #AI #IndustrialMaintenance #EnergyTechnology #HorizonEurope DS2 NOUS CEDAR EU CyclopsProject						
58	Web	Hypertech	Atlantis Engineering showcases PLIADES innovations at the 17th Maintenance Forum and 5th Energia.Tec	25/11/2024	Online	Website's visitors	40 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/11/25/atlantis-participations-october2024/
59	Web	Hypertech	@DS2_EU leads the release of the new report "Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces" with @PLIADESproject, @cedar_eu, @CyclopsProject and @nous_project, showcasing insights from the Data Spaces Cluster at BDVA EBDVF 2024. https://t.co/L1xIAM6j8V	29/11/2024	X	Followers & visitors	16 views		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1862499754447368599
60	Web	Hypertech	📄 New Report Released! We are thrilled to announce the release of "Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces" a report led by DS2 in collaboration with PLIADES project, CEDAR EU, CyclopsProject and NOUS. This report highlights the key takeaways from the Data Spaces Cluster participation at the BDVA EBDVF 2024 in October 2024. The report encapsulates the discussions from the panel session "Interoperability of Data Spaces for Seamless Value Creation Networks" Read the full report here: https://lnkd.in/d_3AujET Sign up in moments: Scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter: https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq #EUOpenData #Dataspaces #Innovation #PLIADESproject #DataSpacesCluster #Interoperability #HorizonEurope	29/11/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 359, Clicks: 12, Click through rate (CTR): 3,34%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 9,47%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7268264394990473216

			DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject PLIADES project NOUS						
61	Web	Hypertech	Enhancing Value Creation Through Interoperable Data Spaces: Insights from the Data Spaces Cluster Report	29/11/2024	Online	Website's visitors	14 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/11/29/ebdvf-data-spaces-cluster-report/
62	Web	Hypertech	<p>📢 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting Recap!</p> <p>Over 50 participants from 27 partner organisations gathered in Graz, Austria AT for a 3-day event packed with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◊ Progress Updates ◊ Use Case Workshops ◊ Hackathon session 🧑‍🔬 ◊ AVL Facility Tour <p>🔗 For more: https://t.co/KtzOWCaYqz</p>	9/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	13 views		https://x.com/PLIADEsproject/status/1866100498425864268
63	Web	Hypertech	<p>🔗 Reflecting on the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting! 📢</p> <p>From 19-21 November 2024, over 50 project members from 27 partner organisations gathered in Graz, Austria, for the 3rd Plenary Meeting of the PLIADES Project, hosted by AVL. This critical gathering of partners drove the project closer to its 12th-month milestone and was packed with technical insights and collaborative problem-solving.</p> <p>Key Highlights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Progress Updates: Status of major deliverables and next steps. ✅ Use Case Workshops: Alignment on data flow integration and technical testing. ✅ Hackathon Success: WP4 Hackathon led by Energy@Work, CEIT, and TNO, enabling participants to collaborate on IDS RAM and connector development ✅ Tour of AVL Facilities: A unique opportunity to explore partner contributions on-site. <p>This 3-day meeting showcased the power of</p>	9/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 398, Clicks: 29, Click through rate (CTR): 7,29%, Likes: 19, Comments: 0, Reposts: 1, Engagement rate: 12,31%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7271864193732005889

			collaboration, innovation, and shared ambition. As we approach our M12 milestone, the team remains committed to driving forward the next generation of AI-enabled data spaces. #PLIADES #DataSpaces #AI #Innovation #Collaboration #PlenaryMeeting #GreenData #DigitalTransformation #HorizonEurope DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS						
64	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES 3rd Plenary Meeting: Milestones Reached, Next Steps Defined	9/12/2024	Online	Website's visitors	51 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/12/09/3rd-plenary-meeting-highlights/
65	Web	Hypertech	📧 The 2nd issue of the #PLIADES newsletter is coming soon! 📅 Don't miss out - sign up now! 🔗 Scroll to the footer of our website & click "Sign up": https://pliades-project.eu	10/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	15 views		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1866431769840628057
66	Web	Hypertech	🚀 Our Sister Project DS2 Needs Your Feedback! 🚀 The DS2 project from the Data Space Cluster is running a quick survey on B2B data sharing, and your insights are essential! 📝 By participating, you'll help shape the future of data spaces and open data initiatives. Let's support DS2 and strengthen the #EUOpenData, #Dataspaces, and #Datauration community!	10/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 89, Clicks: 11, Click through rate (CTR): 12,36%, Likes: 4, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0, Engagement rate: 16,85%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272230541033168896
67	Web	Hypertech	📧 The 2nd issue of the PLIADES newsletter is on its way! 📧 Don't miss out on the latest project updates, key highlights, and exclusive insights from recent activities, including our successful 3rd Plenary Meeting in Graz! ? Not a subscriber yet? Stay ahead of the curve and join our growing community. 🔗 Sign up is quick and easy - scroll to the footer of our website and click "Sign up" to the newsletter: https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq	10/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 141, Clicks: 13, Click through rate (CTR): 9,22%, Likes: 7, Comments: 0, Reposts: 0, Engagement		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272184314631450624

			Be the first to know - subscribe today! #PLIADES #Newsletter #Innovation #Research #StayInformed #HorizonEurope DS2 CEDAR EU CyclopsProject NOUS				rate: 14,18%		
68	Web	Hypertech	📄 New Publication! We're excited to announce PLIADES's first #conference #paper: "Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not- Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data", presented at the 2024 IEEE IST Conference in Tokyo. 🔗 Read more: https://t.co/pPKBsU7ZgV	11/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	13 views		https://x.com/PLIADEsproject/status/1866782035731419628
69	Web	Hypertech	📄 New Publication Alert! We are thrilled to announce the publication of PLIADES project first conference paper: "Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not-Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data". This innovative paper, co-authored by Kosmas Tsiakas, Dimitris Alexiou, Dimitris Giakoumis, Antonis Gasteratos, and Dimitrios Tzovaras, was presented at the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Imaging Systems and Techniques (IST) in Tokyo, Japan. 🔗 Read more here: https://lnkd.in/d59J9_e2 #PLIADES #DataSpaces #AI #Innovation #HorizonEurope #Pedestrians #Annotations #Tracking #Roads #Pipelines #Neural_networks #Autonomous_vehicles	11/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 424, Clicks: 35, Click through rate (CTR): 8,25%, Likes: 20, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 13,44%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272542608164278272

70	Web	Hypertech	PLIADES unveils first conference paper on Automated Data Labelling for Pedestrian Crossing and Not-Crossing Actions Using 3D LiDAR and RGB Data	11/12/2024	Online	Website's visitors	59 views		https://www.pliades-project.eu/2024/12/11/pliades-conference-paper-on-automated-data-labelling/
71	Web	Hypertech	<p>📣 The 2nd PLIADES Newsletter is Out! 📣</p> <p>Don't miss key updates & milestones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔗 IDS-RAM Webinar insights 🔗 EBDVF 2024 showcase 🔗 Partner activities & research <p>📄 Read it here: https://pliades-project.eu/media/</p> <p>📧 Subscribe at the bottom of our website!</p>	13/12/2024	X	Followers & visitors	36 views		https://x.com/PLIADESproject/status/1867508567370006629
72	Web	Hypertech	<p>📣 The 2nd Issue of the PLIADES Newsletter is Out! 📣</p> <p>Discover the latest updates, key milestones, and major achievements from the past few months, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔗 Highlights from the 3rd PLIADES Plenary Meeting 🔗 Insights from the PLIADES Webinar on IDS-RAM 🔗 PLIADES at EBDVF 2024 🔗 Partner Activities & New Research <p>📖 Read the 2nd issue now: https://lnkd.in/dakByjbr</p> <p>📧 Don't miss future updates! Subscribe at the bottom of our website to receive the latest news straight to your inbox. https://lnkd.in/dGKaQesq</p> <p>#PLIADES #Newsletter #DataSpaces #Innovation #AI #Interoperability #HorizonEurope</p>	13/12/2024	LinkedIn	Followers & visitors	Impressions: 126, Clicks: 15, Click through rate (CTR): 11,90%, Likes: 11, Comments: 0, Reposts: 2, Engagement rate: 22,22%		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7273273418056163328